

ENERGY ANALYSIS FOR DISTRIBUTED MACHINE LEARNING ON HPC WITH ITWINAI

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Digital twins offer advantages for scientific research, but their development requires advanced IT skills. CERN is taking part in the interTwin project, in collaboration with other European institutes, to standardize the development, deployment, and testing of digital twins for science and research. As part of this effort, CERN is developing *itwinai*, a framework for scalable machine learning (ML) solutions tailored to data-driven digital twin workflows. The focus is on integrating automated MLOps with high-performance computing (HPC) environments. This includes the adoption of frameworks for distributed deep learning (e.g. Deepspeed, Horovod) and hyper-parameter optimization (e.g. Ray Tune), alongside container technologies like Docker and Singularity to enhance deployment, scalability, and adaptability across diverse computing infrastructures like cloud and HPC.

The focus of this project is to explore energy and resource utilization metrics for distributed machine learning workloads on HPC systems. Specifically, this work investigates the applicability of Perun, a distributed ML metric collection tool. The project involves instrumenting ML training jobs on both single-node and multi-node setups, capturing energy consumption, memory usage, I/O metrics, and analysing scaling, load balancing, and runtime efficiency. This integration aims to provide a more comprehensive view of resource usage and support sustainable, energy-aware ML workflows within the interTwin digital twin environment.

ABSTRACT

Distributed ML workloads on HPC systems are becoming more critical for scientific research, but they come with significant energy and resource costs. Understanding and optimizing these costs is essential for sustainable and efficient training. This project explores the applicability of Perun, a distributed ML metric collection tool, within itwinai and the interTwin digital twin engine. The work instruments ML training runs on single-node and multi-node HPC setups using PyTorch DDP and DeepSpeed, capturing energy consumption, memory usage, utilization, disk I/O, per-device variability, and scaling efficiency. Analyses focus on deviations from ideal speedup and their impact on total energy consumption, revealing communication overheads, load imbalances, and other bottlenecks. We found Perun to be a practical solution for collecting resource consumption metrics in distributed ML training, although data filtering and analysis require additional processing.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Digital Twins

Digital twins are virtual replicas of physical systems designed to predict and model real-world phenomena. They are widely used across industry, in areas such as manufacturing, health-care, retail, and agriculture [15], but also play an important role in scientific research and physics. Examples include simulations for particle detectors, gravitational wave noise models, and environmental forecasting.

Although digital twins are simplified models of real systems, advancements in technology and the growing demand for high-resolution, high-accuracy data have made them increasingly complex and computationally intensive. Managing and analysing such large quantities of data requires significant computational resources and sophisticated software. As a result, many large-scale digital twins now push the limits of available computing capacity.

ML is often employed in digital twin applications to analyse data, identify patterns, and improve the accuracy of the digital replica [12]. Demands for more complex data and models is shifting training from single-GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) to distributed multi-GPU and multi-node configurations. In an ideal scenario, total energy and resource consumption stays the same; if we double the number of GPUs, the training time halves. In practice, however, communication and resource allocation overheads prevent this ideal behaviour. Therefore, ensuring that these models scale efficiently is crucial; inefficiencies at scale can result in large amounts of wasted compute time and energy. Moreover, system complexity can obscure bottlenecks or hidden performance issues. There is a growing need for a tool capable of monitoring, debugging, and evaluating the resource efficiency of ML systems for digital twins.

1.2 itwinai and the interTwin Project

The creators and operators of digital twins are typically experts in their scientific or industrial domains but may not have extensive backgrounds in ML or data science. The interTwin project is a European collaboration that aims to provide a standardised framework for developing and maintaining large-scale scientific digital twins [6]. See Figure 1 for a summary of the interTwin engine and its main use cases.

Figure 1: The interTwin digital twin engine structure (left) and use cases (right)

The interTwin digital twin engine is used to model a variety of scientific use cases, including

gravitational wave noise simulation, drought prediction, wildfire risk forecasting, lattice QCD simulation, and high-energy physics data modelling at CERN. Within the interTwin digital twin engine, itwinai [7] serves as a toolkit for integrating advanced AI and ML workflows on large-scale computing resources. It provides a streamlined workflow for model design, training, monitoring, and hyperparameter optimization on HPC and cloud.

2 BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

2.1 Resource Consumption

Over the past decade, ML has become a computationally intensive field that underpins modern digital twin and scientific applications. A decade ago, only a handful of research groups had access to GPUs capable of training deep neural networks. Today, distributed training on tens or even hundreds of GPUs has become common practice. This scaling is driven by the demand for increasingly large models, high-resolution data, and complex simulation-driven tasks [9].

However, this shift has brought with it a dramatic increase in energy consumption and associated carbon emissions. Training large-scale models now routinely requires days or weeks of runtime across multiple compute nodes. Recent studies have noted the substantial energy footprint of ML training, particularly for models connected to grids powered by fossil fuels [9].

Within scientific research environments such as CERN, understanding and optimizing the energy efficiency of distributed ML is critical. This requires moving beyond simple runtime metrics and developing detailed instrumentation capable of quantifying energy consumption, hardware utilization, and code scalability. Such an analysis enables identification of inefficiencies, bottlenecks, and sustainability trade-offs in distributed training. These insights are essential for both performance tuning and responsible computing.

Relevant metrics during distributed ML training include power and energy consumption, runtime, network traffic, GPU and CPU memory utilisation, and estimated CO_2 emissions. We want to make sure that itwinai users can understand and, ideally, improve the energy footprint of their AI workloads.

2.2 itwinai's Existing Metrics

itwinai records a number of metrics during training, including GPU utilisation, total GPU energy consumption, training epoch time (i.e., how long it takes to do a complete sweep over the whole training dataset), and other profiling metrics meant to measure worker-to-worker communication overheads. The collected metrics are stored in separate log directories, and scalability reports are generated independently. This data can be logged to MLflow [17] for real-time experiment tracking and visualization.

2.3 Perun

Perun [2] is a monitoring and metric collection tool designed specifically for distributed multi-node ML training. Unlike many standard tools that work with a single GPU on a single node, Perun is able to record system-level and per-device metrics across multiple nodes, making it particularly relevant for experiments conducted with itwinai on HPC systems.

Perun collects data at a higher temporal resolution and with greater granularity than itwinai's built-in metric logging. It is compatible with Intel, NVIDIA, and AMD hardware, using libraries and system tools such as nvml, RAPL, psutil, and ROCm SMI [3].

The objective of this project is to evaluate the applicability of Perun for use within itwinai's ML workloads and to determine if it can replace or complement existing metric collection, or whether it is unsuitable for this context.

2.4 Definitions

To contextualize this work, it is useful to define several key concepts related to distributed ML.

2.4.1 Distributed Training

Distributed training refers to the process of training an ML model across multiple computing devices (CPUs and/or GPUs) to accelerate computation and handle large datasets. Parallelism can occur at different levels: data parallelism, model parallelism, or a hybrid of both. In data parallelism, each worker holds a complete copy of the model and processes a different subset of the data, synchronizing gradients after each iteration. In model parallelism, the model itself is distributed across the devices, which is particularly useful for very large models that cannot fit into the memory of a single GPU. The itwinai framework employs data parallelism for its distributed training workflows. See Figure 2 for a depiction of data and model parallelism.

Figure 2: Visual representation of data parallelism and model parallelism, both examples of distributed training [13]

itwinai enables distributed data parallel training by providing a unified interface to the following popular frameworks: Horovod [4], DeepSpeed [1], and PyTorch Distributed Data Parallel [11].

2.4.2 CPU vs GPU

Machine learning models can be trained on CPUs or GPUs, with GPUs generally providing much faster parallel computation for tensor operations. However, CPU-based training remains relevant for smaller models, data preprocessing, or cases where GPUs are unavailable. Moreover, distributed ML frameworks remain flexible to operate efficiently across both CPU and GPU hardware architectures.

2.4.3 Single-node vs Multi-node

In HPC, a node is a server unit containing computing hardware. A node comprises CPUs, RAM, local storage, network interfaces, and it will typically have 0 or 4-8 GPUs [16]. Communication between devices within a node is fast and easy, since each device is aware of the other devices on the node and can communicate via high-speed interconnect (e.g., NVLink [10]). However, the training is then limited to the number of GPUs available on a single node.

Single-node training typically involves a master process that spawns a worker process for each GPU on the node. This master process oversees communication, including data splitting and gradient synchronization, while the worker processes take care of model training.

Multi-node configurations, on the other hand, involve inter-node communication over the network, typically using InfiniBand or Slingshot interconnect. This type of training introduces additional complexity due to higher communication latency, network contention, and the need for synchronization across physically separate machines. However, it allows training to scale to dozens or even hundreds of GPUs.

Multi-node training requires an additional process to launch master processes for each node. Devices within a node only have node-specific context, so awareness of global and local worker ranks must be properly communicated and agreed upon by all the workers at the beginning. There are different launchers and strategies available to enable this inter-node communication.

In this project, we use single device, single-node, and multi-node setups to account for the varying needs of itwinai users.

2.4.4 Training Configuration

In the context of itwinai, a *training configuration* refers to a combination of distribution launchers, strategies, and hardware. These three are required to describe the specific setup used for a distributed training job. See Figure 3 for a visualization of these configurations.

- **Launcher** - defines how worker processes are created and coordinated. These are protocols that spawn workers, assign ranks, and initialize communication. They are frequently used in ML training, but are not specific to ML. itwinai supports the launchers: `torchrun` and `mpirun`.
- **Strategy** - specifies how ML training is performed and synchronized. These protocols are responsible for partitioning the dataset across devices and synchronizing gradients during training. itwinai supports the following strategies: PyTorch Distributed Data Parallel (DDP) [11], DeepSpeed [1], and Horovod [4].
- **Hardware** - indicates the computational resources used. The hardware can be CPU-only or GPU-accelerated, single device, single-node, or multi-node. itwinai supports all of these options.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Goal

The principal objective of this work is to explore the use of Perun as a resource-centered metric collection and analysis tool for the itwinai project. The goal is to log and analyse configuration parameters, such as number of devices, nodes, launcher, strategy, and hardware type, as well

Figure 3: The three components of distributed training configuration: Launchers, Strategies, and Hardware

as runtime resource metrics like epoch time, total training time, GPU energy consumption, memory usage, I/O, and device utilization. With this data, we can track improvements, identify optimal setups, and uncover bugs or inefficiencies.

3.2 Training Configuration Setup

We conducted training with a simple convolutional neural network (CNN) with two convolutional layers and two fully connected layers. We trained the model on the MNIST dataset, a widely recognized benchmark dataset for ML [14].

Initially, we planned to execute Perun on all training configurations supported by itwinaï. However, Perun is still in development, and is not currently compatible with the `torchrun` launcher, and in turn, the PyTorch DDP distribution strategy. In addition, we opted not to include Horovod within the scope of this project.

Therefore, we used `mpirun` launcher and DeepSpeed strategy in our training configuration. For both CPU-only and GPU-accelerated hardware configurations, we trained models on single device (1 GPU), single-node (2 and 4 GPUs), and multi-node (8, 16, and 32 GPUs).

We conducted all experiments in two HPC clusters: Jülich’s JUWELS Booster (JSC) in Germany [8] and Vega in Slovenia [5].

3.3 Integrating Perun

Given the above ML distribution configuration, we integrated Perun’s tracking features to gather and evaluate data. Instrumentation was initially implemented using Perun’s command-line interface (CLI) and later via its Python API, which consists of several function decorators.

Perun produces a recursive hierarchical data format version 5 (HDF5) output: at the lowest level are raw sensor and device metrics (e.g., per-GPU power draw, host memory usage, I/O counters), which are aggregated upward by device, then node, then run, then application (see Figure 4). Although processing this output requires more effort than itwinaï’s aggregated logs, the enhanced granularity enables device-level and time-series analyses not previously available. We used Perun’s default output and Python scripting to parse the HDF5 structure, extract relevant metrics, and generate visual reports. See Figure 5 for an example of a human-readable report showing metrics such as GPU power consumption and memory utilization along with estimated CO_2 emissions and cost.

Figure 4: A breakdown of Perun’s recursive output file structure [2]

```

App name: train
First run: 2025-08-06T11:43:25.643681
Last run: 2025-08-06T15:11:43.212681

RUN ID: 2025-08-06T15:11:43.212681

Round # |  RUNTIME |  ENERGY |  POWER | GPU_POWER | GPU_MEM | DRAM_MEM |
-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|
      0 | 14.630 s | 3.838 kJ | 262.113 W | 262.113 W | 2.898 GB | 28.799 GB |
      0 | 14.630 s | 3.838 kJ | 262.113 W | 262.113 W | 2.898 GB | 28.799 GB |

Application Summary

The application has been run 4 times. In total, it has used 0.007 kWh, released a
total of 0.002 kgCO2e into the atmosphere, and you paid 0.00 € in electricity for
it.
    
```

Figure 5: An example of a human-readable Perun output report

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

4.1 Results

The following figures and discussion demonstrate how Perun can be used to derive deeper insights and metrics complementary to those currently collected by itwinai.

4.1.1 Compatibility with itwinai

As a first step, a sanity check was conducted to verify that Perun’s metric collection aligns with itwinai’s existing scalability analysis. Ensuring compatibility is essential for integrating Perun and itwinai.

The top panel of Figure 6 displays itwinai’s speedup and epoch time plots, while the bottom panel shows the same metrics generated from Perun’s training runs. The comparable graphs confirm that Perun’s output is consistent with itwinai’s measurements. In these plots itwinai workloads were run on GPUs, whereas Perun workloads were on CPUs.

4.1.2 Complementary Metrics

Perun also collects additional system metrics that are not currently captured by itwinai. For example, it provides insights into CPU utilization while itwinai collects GPU utilization.

In Figure 7, the left panel illustrates itwinai’s GPU utilization for different distributed ML strategies and hardware configurations, while the right panel presents CPU utilization data

Figure 6: Top: itwinai’s internally generated scalability reports for speedup and epoch time (generated on GPU). Bottom: comparable reports generated with Perun-only data (generated on CPU)

collected by Perun during similar training runs. This additional context helps identify whether the CPU acts as a bottleneck or remains underutilized during GPU-intensive workloads.

Figure 7: GPU utilization bar chart generated by itwinai (left) and CPU utilization chart generated with Perun data (right).

4.1.3 Further Insights

Perun’s primary advantage is its high-resolution metric collection, recording data for each individual GPU rather than aggregating results across all devices, as is currently done by itwinai. This enables fine-grained analysis of energy distribution, scaling efficiency, and load balancing factors that are otherwise obscured when metrics are averaged during a run.

Scalability and Energy Consumption. Analysis of Perun’s data reveals the connection between sub-optimal speedup and increased energy consumption. Figure 8 shows a stacked

graph, with the top panel indicating how the average epoch time deviates from the ideal linear speedup (with a shaded region indicating the deviation), and the bottom panel displaying total and per-worker energy consumption.

Figure 8: Deviation from ideal linear speedup (top) and total and per-worker energy consumption (bottom), both generated with Perun.

In an ideal scenario, doubling the number of GPUs should halve the epoch time. However, in practice, this scaling is limited by factors such as communication latency, network contention, and memory overhead. These inefficiencies lead to sub-linear scaling, where runtime reduction is not enough to offset the additional energy consumed. Consequently, total job energy increases even as runtime decreases, indicating reduced energy efficiency. In this use case, it would be more energy-efficient to use fewer GPUs, as the scaling overhead outweighs the runtime gains.

Load Balancing. Another valuable insight revealed by Perun is the ability to assess load balancing across GPUs. A well-balanced workload should result in similar energy consumption per device, whereas imbalances indicate that certain GPUs are performing disproportionately more work while others remain idle.

The boxplot in Figure 9 illustrates per-worker energy consumption for different GPU counts. While the average per-GPU energy decreases as more GPUs are added, the reduction is not perfectly proportional, suggesting imperfect workload distribution as previously discussed. The spread of the error bars indicates the degree of imbalance; a wide spread reflects uneven energy usage among GPUs, whereas a narrow spread implies efficient load balancing.

For example, at 4 GPUs, load balancing was least efficient, with the lowest-consuming worker using about 1.5 Wh and the highest using about 2.25 Wh. As the GPU count increased, this imbalance diminished, suggesting improved parallel efficiency at larger scales. Identifying such disparities provides a valuable diagnostic tool for developers, helping them optimize distributed training configurations to minimize idle time, reduce wasted energy, and improve overall performance.

Figure 9: Per-worker GPU energy consumption by number of GPUs.

4.2 Benefits

With appropriate modification and customization, Perun provides a clean wrapper and API, reducing the need for manual probing of metrics. This simplifies data collection compared to itwinai’s current approach.

Perun captures supplementary information not currently collected by itwinai, such as CPU utilization and other host-level metrics. This additional data enables users to detect potential bottlenecks and better understand hardware-level behavior during training.

Perun collects timestamped metrics per device, offering a more granular view compared to itwinai’s aggregated reports. This high-resolution data facilitates more advanced and insightful analyses. Providing detailed information about energy consumption, utilization, and scaling behavior, Perun enables users to debug performance issues and optimize distributed training configurations in ways that were not previously possible with itwinai alone.

4.3 Limitations

Although Perun collects detailed metrics, significant preprocessing and filtering are required before meaningful analyses can be performed, introducing additional work.

Collecting CPU energy consumption often requires administrator (root) privileges or access to protected files (e.g., `/sys/powercap`), limiting its applicability in many HPC environments where users have limited permissions.

Using Perun as a wrapper or decorator introduces additional runtime overhead, mostly due to setup and cleanup operations. While energy impact is minimal, the extra time can be noticeable in large-scale experiments.

The current Perun implementation does not fully support the `torchrun` launcher and is not able to properly handle multiple workers created by `torchrun`, resulting in a race condition where multiple processes attempt to write to the same files simultaneously.

By default, Perun saves metrics only at the end of a training run, meaning that data is lost if the job fails prematurely. Additionally, this prevents live monitoring of scaling efficiency or resource utilization during runtime. However, Perun is expected to soon be compatible with live logging tools such as MLflow, remedying this problem.

4.4 Conclusion

Based on the analyses performed, Perun is a viable tool for collecting high-resolution resource consumption metrics during distributed ML training on HPC clusters with itwinai. In this work, we integrated Perun into ML workflows on two HPC systems across a range of configurations, varying the type and number of GPUs, CPUs, nodes, and launchers. Using Perun’s high-resolution, per-device metric collection, we analysed runtime performance, energy consumption, and load balancing behavior, generating new insights into scaling behavior and energy trade-offs that are not visible through aggregated metrics alone. However, Perun is best used as a complement rather than a full replacement, as it provides additional metrics and finer granularity while itwinai’s internal metric collection remains a reliable backbone for scalability and performance reporting.

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